

Not Accessible with Mobile

This survey can not be filled out using a mobile device.

Accessing this survey via a mobile phone greatly decreases the survey experience and the quality of the generated data.

We kindly ask you to open this link again from a computer.

Intro

Welcome to the research study on phishing and risk management! We are glad you are here.

This survey will require approximately 10-15 minutes of your time.

DISCLAIMER: Please mind that accessing this survey via a mobile phone greatly decreases the survey experience and the quality of the generated data.

We strongly advise you to only access this survey from a computer. If you are currently opening this from a mobile phone, please consider closing the survey and starting it from you computer.

Informed consent

Please read the informed consent below and click next if you agree.

Informed consent

- You must be at least 16 years old to participate in the study.
- All data collected is anonymized, meaning that the data cannot be traced back to you.
- This survey does not pose any risk to you.
- Your participation is entirely voluntary.
- Should you at any time choose to withdraw from this study, you are allowed to do so.
- You can voluntarily participate in a raffle after finishing this survey.

By clicking "Agree" you agree with the above and hereby provide your consent to share the anonymised data for research purposes.

Interest and Knowledge in the topic of phishing

Before you start, we would like to ask you about your interest and knowledge in the topic of phishing.

I am interested in the topic of phishing

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I feel confident in my ability to correctly identify phishing threats

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I feel confident in my ability to correctly assess the risk of phishing e-mails

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Question Phishing 1

Do you know what phishing is?

- Yes
- No

Question Phishing 2

Phishing is...

- the practice in which an attacker sends an enormous amount of data to a specific website, intending to shut down the website and make it unavailable for users.
- the practice in which an attacker sends fraudulent messages to users to trick them into revealing their personal information. It is usually performed through email, convincing the user to click on a malicious link or attachment.
- the practice in which an attacker repeatedly attempts to guess the password of a user, by using numerous combinations of numbers, letters, and symbols until the password is discovered.

Instructions 1

Instructions:

This survey contains **2 sets** of phishing questions. Each set contains **8 questions** and has **no time limit**. A **training video** about phishing will be presented between the two sets of questions.

For this research study, you will play the role of **2 personas**: a Chief Technology Officer and a Human Resource Trainee that work at the same media company. Both of these personas are targets of **phishing** and **spear phishing** emails. For each persona, background information is provided about their phishing identification expertise.

Each set will start by presenting one of the two personas, followed by four phishing identification questions. Then you will be presented with the other persona and another four phishing identification questions. Each question consists of assessing a fictional email and identifying if it is a phishing attempt. You will be prompted to answer if the email in question is a phishing

attempt and assess the risk it poses to the company, considering the persona in case.

Instructions 2 (Example)

In the following you will be presented with an example of a mail that you might receive.

For each mail you will be provided with the real website and email domain of the sender or company at the top of the page.

In some situations the email will be displayed as following:

<department>@<company>.com

or

<name_lastname>@<department>.<company>.com

This means that the customerservice department of "MyCompany" would have the email address of:

customerservice@mycompany.com

Or that Sally Walsh, working in sales for a company named "TheCompany" would have the email domain of:

sally_walsh@sales.thecompany.com.

Furthermore, all links that are shown in the mail have a corresponding box at the bottom of the page indicating where this link directs to.

This is shown because sometimes a blue underlined hyperlink actually directs to a different website than what is indicated in the text.

Even though this will only be the case in some mails, you will be shown this box in every mail. You can see an example of this in the image below.

BY PROCEEDING TO THE NEXT PAGE, YOU WILL BE INTRODUCED TO THE PERSONAS AND START THE PHISHING IDENTIFICATION TASK.

from **Name** (<name_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Name,

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Proin eget nisi condimentum, faucibus orci eu, convallis dolor. Maecenas ut rhoncus nunc. Aenean iaculis tortor nulla. Nam est velit, viverra sed pellentesque quis, accumsan et sapien:

www.shorturl.com/2834

Suspendisse vel quam sit amet sem sagittis efficitur.

Kind regards,
Name Lastname

The clickable link directs to:

(www.example.com/example)

Jesse Persona

Chief Technology Officer (CTO)

You take on the role of Jesse Walsh, the Chief Technology Officer (CTO) of Myers Media Design. You have a lot of experience with detecting phishing threats since you already participated in multiple phishing trainings. You come into the office this morning, sit down at your desk, and look through your mailbox. You have an important meeting coming up in 5 minutes and quickly try to assess which mails require your attention before you go into the meeting.

1-Phishing Task 1 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

NiceStuff website domain: www.nicestuff.com

NiceStuff email domain: <department>@nicestuff.com

from **NiceStuff Customer Service** (service@nicestuff.com)
to me ▾

Good Morning,

There has been an issue with your order (ID 8231) at NiceStuff.com. We are trying to resend the parcel but need you to verify the process. To receive your parcel please log in with the link provided below and confirm your order:

www.service24.net/16zt31y

Kind Regards,

NiceStuff
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

www.service24.net/16zt31y

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

1-Phishing Task 2 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

Trackr website domain: www.trackr.com

Trackr email domain: <department>@trackr.com

from **Trackr** (notify@trackr.com)
to me ▾

Hello Jesse,

You have an unread message from Winston Bird in your Trackr inbox. View your messages here:

www.trackr.com/login/messages

This is an automated message, do not reply to this email. If you no longer want to be notified about missed activity on Trackr, please change your setting under the following link:

www.trackr.com/login/settings

Have a great day,
Your Trackr team

The clickable link directs to:

(www.trackr.net/login/messages)

The clickable link directs to:

(www.trackr.net/login/settings)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

1-Phishing Task 3 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

FairShare website domain: www.fairshare.com

FairShare email domain: <department>@fairshare.com

from FairShare (customerservice@fairshare.com)
to me ▾

Dear Customer,

As the safety of our customers is of utmost importance, we require every user to reset their password after 6 months. Please click the following link to set a new password or your account will be temporarily deactivated.

<https://tinyurl.com/tcye4j74x>*

*This Website uses a link shortening service for user friendliness.

Best Regards,

FairShare
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

www.fairshare.com/login/password

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

1-Phishing Task 5 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

MyAgenda website domain: www.myagenda.com

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from Alex (alex_smith@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Jesse,

For the upcoming meeting we have slightly adjusted the agenda. Could you have a look at it and let me know whether there need to be any final adjustments?

www.myagenda.com/mmd/meetings

Kind regards,
Alex

P.S The faster the feedback we get from you, the easier will be to organize the meeting for the last trimester.

The clickable link directs to:

myagenda.com/mmd/meetings

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

Sam Persona

Human Resource Trainee

You take on the role of Sam Silverstein, who has just graduated and is now the newly employed Trainee in the Human Resource Team at Myers Media Design. This is your first time working in such a position and you never participated in a phishing training. You come into the office this morning, sit down at your desk, and look through your mailbox. You have an important meeting coming up in 5 minutes and quickly try to assess which mails require your attention before you go into the meeting.

1-Phishing Task 4 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

VideoWorld website domain: www.videoworld.com

VideoWorld email domain: <department>@videoworld.com

from **VideoWorld** (noreply@videoworld.com)
to me ▾

Dear customer,

There was a problem with your automatic payment.
Your subscription will end soon.

If you wish to continue using VideoWorld, please update your
payment method using the following link:

videoworld.com/payment

Kind regards,
The VideoWorld Team

The clickable link directs to:

(www.videoworld.net/payment)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

1-Phishing Task 6 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from **Luca** (luca_morgan@hr.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hi Sam,

You might have heard of our learning hub where we offer courses and trainings to give all our employees the chance to advance in their professional career by learning new and important skills.

We also regularly schedule our recurring security trainings using this website, so it is important that you set up an account to make sure you will not miss out on these trainings!

In the attached PDF file you can find a thorough explanation how to set up your account.

Kind Regards,
Luca Morgan
Head of HR
Myers Media

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

1-Phishing Task 7 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

TalkNet website domain: www.talknet.com

TalkNet email domain: <department>@talknet.com

from TalkNet (customerservice@talknet.com)
to me ▾

Dear Customer,

We are changing some of our offers. Sadly, the data plan you are currently using will no longer be offered in the future.

However, you can now upgrade to one of our newer, better dataplans without any fee! You can choose from:

- BusinessEU20+
- BusinessEU20 Extra
- TalknetFamily+
- FreeRoam Plan

If you would like to learn more about our offers you can use the following link:

www.talknet.com/offers

If you already have a plan in mind and want to upgrade your plan free of charge, simply follow this link:

www.talknet.com/offers/upgrade

Kind regards,
TalkNet Customer Service

The clickable link directs to:

www.talknet.com/offers

The clickable link directs to:

www.talknet.com/offers/upgrade

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

1-Phishing Task 8 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Google Meet website domain: <https://meet.google.com>

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from Alex (alex.smith@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Sam,

This might be short notice, but there seems to be an issue with setting up meetings in zoom today. We will instead use google meets today which you can access via this link:

Alex Smith is inviting you to an ongoing video call.

Topic: Zoom meeting substitution

Join ongoing Call

<https://meet.google.com/qkr-wpye-nvp.com>

See you in a few,
Alex Smith

The clickable link directs to:

(<https://meet.google.com/qkr-wpye-nvp.com>)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

Training F

Thank you for completing the first part of the survey!

You now get to watch a short instructional video in which you learn about the risk of phishing mails and the identification thereof.

Afterwards, you will be asked to identify eight more mails as phishing or not and assess their risk.

Watch the video carefully!

After finishing the video you can proceed to the next page.

Training M

Thank you for completing the first part of the survey!

You now get to watch a short instructional video in which you learn about the risk of phishing mails and the identification thereof. Afterwards, you will be asked to identify eight more mails as phishing or not and assess their risk.

Watch the video carefully!

After finishing the video you can proceed to the next page.

Instructions 2

Instructions:

- Thank you for watching this short instructional video.
- The second set of this survey also has a total of **8 questions** and has **no time limit**. Each question consists in assessing a fictional email and identifying if it is a phishing attempt.
- Similarly to the first set, it will start by presenting a persona, followed by four phishing identification questions. Then you will see the second persona and another four questions. Each question consists of assessing a fictional email and identifying if it is a phishing attempt. You will be prompted to answer if the email in question is a phishing attempt and the risk it poses to the persona in case.

BY PROCEEDING TO THE NEXT PAGE, YOU WILL START THE PHISHING IDENTIFICATION TASK.

A-Phishing Task 4 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

MMD noreply email domain: noreply@myersmedia.com

MMD website domain: www.myersmedia.com

MMD alternative domain: www.myersmediadesign.com

from **Myers Media Design** (noreply@myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Dear employee,

We are currently changing the domain of our website. In the next days, the old domain will be discontinued and not accessible anymore.

To access the new Myers Media Design website, refer to:
www.myersmediadesign.com

Kind Regards,
Myers Media Design

The clickable link directs to:

www.myersmediadesign.com

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

A-Phishing Task 6 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Design School billing email address: billingservice@designschool.com

from DesignSchool Billing Service (billingservice@designschool.com)

to me ▾

Dear Sam,

Thank you for participating in the workshop! We hope you could learn a lot and look forward to working with you again soon.

This email contains a receipt with the description of the extra hours invested and the consequent payment regarding the workshop on advanced InDesign skills. This information is annexed to the email through a PDF file.

We would kindly ask you to have a look at the file to confirm that all the hours booked are correct and we have filled in the correct billing information.

Best Regards,

DesignSchool
Customer Service Department

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

A-Phishing Task 7 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

CreatorsNet website domain: www.creators.net

CreatorsNet noreply domain: noreply@creatorsnet.com

from **CreatorsNet** (noreply@creatorsnet.com)
to me ▾

Dear Customer,

CreatorsNet is updating its security measurements. In the next 15 days all users need to change their passwords. The new password needs to follow this specific guidelines:

- Length between 6-18 characters.
- Have at least one symbol such as '!', '?', '@', etc.
- Have at least one capital letter
- Have at least one digit.

Users that don't change their password in period of time mentioned above will have their accounts frozen as a safety measure. In the case, that your account got frozen you can go to: www.creators.net/account

The password can be changed using the link below: www.creators.net/account/password

Best Regards,

CreatorsNet Service

The clickable link directs to:

www.creators.net/account

The clickable link directs to:

www.creators.net/account/password

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None Low Medium High

A-Phishing Task 8 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Zoom Invite Link: www.live.zoom.us/<meeting code>

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from **Alex** (alex_smith@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Sam,

The marketing directors are currently meeting via Zoom and some issue came up about the layout of the magazine we are currently working on. Do you have the availability to quickly brief them on this urgent matter.

The link to the Zoom meeting is the following:

Alex Smith is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting.

Topic: Urgent meeting

Join Zoom Meeting

www.live.zoom.us/j/91erjhjhrw

Dial by your location

+31 707 006 526 Netherlands

+31 20 241 0288 Netherlands

(...)

The clickable link directs to:

www.live.zoom.us/j/91erjhjhrw

Best Regards,

Alex Smith

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

A-Phishing Task 1 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

PowerParts website domain: www.powerparts.com

PowerParts email domain: <department>@powerparts.com

from **PowerParts Customer Service** (customerservice@smartcards.com)
to me ▾

Good Evening,

The order with id 5678 has not been delivered. To resend this order within the next 24h, refer to the link below:

www.sale77.to/13yu2oqa

Best Regards,

PowerParts
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

(www.sale77.to/13yu2oqa)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

WIP A-Phishing Task 2 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

MMD website domain: www.myersmedia.com

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from Alex (alex.smith@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Jesse,

Unfortunately, I'm facing some issues accessing the company portal. I have already created a ticket via the website with our IT-service where you can check the details:

www.myersmediadesign.com/tickets/92331

If you don't now how the ticket system works you can find more information here:

www.myersmediadesign.com/tickets/help

Thanks in advance,
Alex Smith

The clickable link directs to:

www.myersmediadesign.com/tickets/92331

The clickable link directs to:

www.myersmediadesign.com/tickets/help

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

A-Phishing Task 3 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

PowerParts website domain: www.powerparts.com

PowerParts email domain: <department>@powerparts.com

from **PowerParts Customer Service** (customerservice@powerparts.com)
to me ▾

Good Morning,

The requested item with ID-1234 has returned to stock and can be delivered in the next 24 hours. Due to the immense popularity over this item, it is advised to order it as soon as possible, as this item goes out of stock frequently.

To purchase it directly from the item store page, proceed to the link below:

<https://tinyurl.com/ycyu5y3z> *

*This Website uses a link shortening service for user friendliness.

Best Regards,

PowerParts
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

www.powerparts.com/items/1234

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

A-Phishing Task 5 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

Google Drive website domain: www.drive.google.com

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from **Kim** (kim_marshall@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Jesse,

I hereby send the trimester report about the sales we've got on the #A65 product.

www.drive.google.com/drive/u/1/10dsgifjgpjregw4gCl

Best Regards,

Kim Marsh

P.S You should really take a look as there were some problems regarding some software bug while booting.

The clickable link directs to:

[\(www.drive.google.com/drive/u/1/10dsgifjgpjregw4gCl\)](http://www.drive.google.com/drive/u/1/10dsgifjgpjregw4gCl)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

B-Phishing Task 1 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

PowerParts website domain: www.powerparts.com

PowerParts email domain: <department>@powerparts.com

from **PowerParts Customer Service** (customerservice@powerparts.com)
to me ▾

Good Evening,

The order with id 5678 has not been delivered. To resend this order within the next 24h, refer to the link below:

www.powerparts.com/orders

Best Regards,

PowerParts
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

(www.powerparts.com/orders)

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

WIP B-Phishing Task 2 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

MMD website domain: www.myersmedia.com

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from Alex (alex.smith@devops.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Jesse,

Unfortunately, I'm facing some issues accessing the company portal. I have already created a ticket via the website with our IT-service where you can check the details:

www.ticket-service.myermedia.com/tickets/92331

If you don't now how the ticket system works you can find more information here:

www.ticket-service.myermedia.com/tickets/help

Thanks in advance,
Alex Smith

The clickable link directs to:

www.ticket-service.myermedia.com/tickets/92331

The clickable link directs to:

www.ticket-service.myermedia.com/tickets/help

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

B-Phishing Task 3 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

PowerParts website domain: www.powerparts.com

PowerParts email domain: <department>@powerparts.com

from **PowerParts Customer Service** (customerservice@powerparts.com)
to me ▾

Good Morning,

The requested item with ID-1234 has returned to stock and can be delivered in the next 24 hours.

Due to the immense popularity over this item, it is advised to order it as soon as possible, as this item goes out of stock frequently.

To purchase it directly from the item store page, proceed to the link below:

www.powerparts.com/items/1234

Best Regards,

PowerParts
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

www.powerparts.com/items/1234

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None Low Medium High

B-Phishing Task 5 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

Google Drive website domain: www.drive.google.com

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from **Kim** (kim_marshall@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Jesse,

I hereby send the trimester report about the sales we've got on the #A65 product.

www.drive.google.com/drive/u/1/10dsgio2o3itfeg3dK4gCl

Best Regards,

Kim Marsh

P.S You should really take a look as there were some problems regarding some software bug while booting.

The clickable link directs to:

[\(www.drive.google.com/drive/u/1/10dsgifjgppjregw4gCl\)](http://www.drive.google.com/drive/u/1/10dsgifjgppjregw4gCl)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

B-Phishing Task 4 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

MMD noreply email domain: noreply@myersmedia.com

MMD website domain: www.myersmedia.com

MMD alternative domain: www.myersmediadesign.com

from **Safety Dispatcher** (safetydispatcher@gmail.com)
to me ▾

Dear employee,

We are currently changing the domain of our website. In the next days, the old domain will be discontinued and not accessible anymore.

To access the new website domain refer to:
www.alternativeportal.me/13yu2oqa

Kind Regards

The clickable link directs to:

www.alternativeportal.me/13yu2oqa

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

B-Phishing Task 6 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Design School billing email address: billingservice@designschool.com

From **DesignSchool Billing Service** (customerservice@designscool.com)

to me ▾

Dear Sam,

Thank you for participating in the workshop! We hope you could learn a lot and look forward to working with you again soon.

This email contains a receipt with the description of the extra hours invested and the consequent payment regarding the workshop on advanced InDesign skills. This information is annexed to the email through a PDF file.

We would kindly ask you to have a look at the file to confirm that all the hours booked are correct and we have filled in the correct billing information.

Best Regards,

DesignSchool
Customer Service Department

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

B-Phishing Task 7 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

CreatorsNet website domain: www.creators.net

CreatorsNet email domain: noreply@creatorsnet.com

from **CreatorsNet** (noreply@creatorsnet.com)
to me ▾

Dear Customer,

CreatorsNet is updating its security measurements. In the next 15 days all users need to change their passwords. The new password needs to follow this specific guidelines:

- Length between 6-18 characters.
- Have at least one symbol such as '!', '?', '@', etc.
- Have at least one capital letter
- Have at least one digit.

Users that don't change their password in period of time mentioned above will have their accounts frozen as a safety measure. In the case, that your account got frozen you can go to: www.creators.net/account

The password can be changed using the link below: www.creators.net/account/password

Best Regards,

Myers Media Design

The clickable link directs to:

www.creators.net/account

The clickable link directs to:

www.creators.net/account/password

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

B-Phishing Task 8 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Zoom Invite Link: www.live.zoom.us/<meeting code>

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from **Alex** (alex_smith@marketing.myersrmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Sam,

The marketing directors are currently meeting via Zoom and some issue came up about the layout of the magazine we are currently working on. Do you have the availability to quickly brief them on this urgent matter.

The link to the Zoom meeting is the following:

Alex Smith is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting.

Topic: Urgent meeting

Join Zoom Meeting

www.live.zoorn.us/j/91erjhjhrw

Dial by your location

+31 707 006 526 Netherlands

+31 20 241 0288 Netherlands

(...)

The clickable link directs to:

www.live.zoorn.us/j/91erjhjhrw

Best Regards,

Alex Smith

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 1 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

NiceStuff website domain: www.nicestuff.com

NiceStuff email domain: <department>@nicestuff.com

from **NiceStuff Customer Service** (customerservice@nicestuff.com)
to me ▾

Good Morning,

There has been an issue with your order (ID 8231) at NiceStuff.com. We are trying to resend the parcel but need you to verify the process. To receive your parcel please log in with the link provided below and confirm your order:

www.nicestuff.com/verify

Kind Regards,

NiceStuff
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

www.nicestuff.com/verify

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 2 (P)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

Trackr website domain: www.trackr.com

Trackr email domain: <department>@trackr.com

from **Trackr** (notify@gmail.com)
to me ▾

Hello Jesse,

You have an unread message from Winston Bird in your Trackr inbox. View your messages here:

www.traccker.net/login/messages

This is an automated message, do not reply to this email. If you no longer want to be notified about missed activity on Trackr, please change your setting under the following link:

www.traccker.net/login/settings

Have a great day,
Your Trackr team

The clickable link directs to:

(www.traccker.net/login/messages)

The clickable link directs to:

(www.traccker.net/login/settings)

Does this email contain phishing?

Yes

No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 3 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

FairShare website domain: www.fairshare.com

FairShare email domain: <department>@fairshare.com

from FairShare (customerservice@fairshare.com)
to me ▾

Dear Customer,

As the safety of our customers is of utmost importance, we require every user to reset their password after 6 months. Please click the following link to set a new password or your account will be temporarily deactivated.

www.fairshare.com/login/password

Best Regards,

FairShare
Customer Service Department

The clickable link directs to:

www.fairshare.com/login/password

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 5 (NP)

Jesse - CTO

Relevant Information:

MyAgenda website domain: www.myagenda.com

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from Alex (alex.smith@marketing.myersmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Jesse,

For the upcoming meeting we have slightly adjusted the agenda. Could you have a look at it and let me know whether there need to be any final adjustments?

www.myagenda.com/mmd/meetings

Kind regards,
Alex

P.S The faster the feedback we get from you, the easier will be to organize the meeting for the last trimester.

The clickable link directs to:

(myagenda.com/mmd/meetings)

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 4 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

VideoWorld website domain: www.videoworld.com

VideoWorld email domain: <department>@videoworld.com

from VideoWorld (noreply@e120er23jyn2.com)
to me ▾

Dear customer,

There was a problem with your automatic payment.
Your subscription will end soon.

If you wish to continue using VideoWorld, please update your
payment method using the following link:

www.vidworld.net/payment

Kind regards,
The VideoWorld Team

The clickable link directs to:

(www.vidworld.net/payment)

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 6 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from **Luca** (luca_morgan@yahoo.com)
to me ▾

Hi Sam,

You might have heard of our learning hub where we offer courses and trainings to give all our employees the chance to advance in their professional career by learning new and important skills.

We also regularly schedule our recurring security trainings using this website, so it is important that you set up an account to make sure you will not miss out on these trainings!

In the attached PDF file you can find a thorough explanation how to set up your account.

Kind Regards,
Luca Morgan
Head of HR
Myers Media

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
 No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

2-Phishing Task 7 (NP)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

TalkNet website domain: www.talknet.com

TalkNet email domain: <department>@talknet.com

from TalkNet (customerservice@talknet.com)
to me ▾

Dear Customer,

We are changing some of our offers. Sadly, the data plan you are currently using will no longer be offered in the future.

However, you can now upgrade to one of our newer, better dataplans without any fee! You can choose from:

- BusinessEU20+
- BusinessEU20 Extra
- TalknetFamily+
- FreeRoam Plan

If you would like to learn more about our offers you can use the following link:

www.talknet.com/offers

If you already have a plan in mind and want to upgrade your plan free of charge, simply follow this link:

www.talknet.com/offers/upgrade

Kind regards,
TalkNet Customer Service

The clickable link directs to:

www.talknet.com/offers

The clickable link directs to:

www.talknet.com/offers/upgrade

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None Low Medium High

2-Phishing Task 8 (P)

Sam - Human Resource Trainee

Relevant Information:

Google Meet website domain: <https://meet.google.com>

Myersmedia email address:

<firstname_lastname>@<department>.myersmedia.com

from Alex (alex.smith@marketing.myersrmedia.com)
to me ▾

Hey Sam,

This might be short notice, but there seems to be an issue with setting up meetings in zoom today. We will instead use google meets today which you can access via this link:

Alex Smith is inviting you to an ongoing video call.

Topic: Zoom meeting substitution

Join ongoing Call

<https://meet.google.com/qkr-wpye-nvp.com>

See you in a few,
Alex Smith

The clickable link directs to:

(<https://meet.google.com/qkr-wpye-nvp.com>)

Does this email contain phishing?

- Yes
- No

From the perspective of the employer, what risk does this email pose to the employer?

None

Low

Medium

High

Control Questions

For a final round of questions, we would like to know a little bit about how you experienced the phishing training video.

I had a sufficient understanding of the task (identifying phishing emails and their risk).

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Somewhat disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat agree

Agree

Strongly agree

I received sufficient information to complete all the tasks.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Somewhat disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat agree

Agree

Strongly agree

I feel confident in my ability to correctly identify phishing threats.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I feel confident in my ability to correctly assess the risk of phishing e-mails.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Presenter Questions

What gender did you imagine Sam (HRT) as?

- Male
- Female
- Other:

What gender did you imagine Jesse (CTO) as?

- Male
- Female
- Other:

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
The presenter was qualified to teach about this topic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter was professional	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter was knowledgeable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter was confident	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter was attractive	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter was persuasive	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter had a pleasant voice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter spoke too fast	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The presenter spoke too monotone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Demographics

We kindly ask you to answer a few questions about yourself in the last part of the survey.

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Other

Have you been diagnosed with a reading disorder?

- Yes
- No

What is your nationality?

Which of the following best describes you?

- Asian or Pacific Islander
- Black or African American
- Hispanic or Latino
- Native American or Alaskan Native
- White or Caucasian
- Multiracial or Biracial
- A race/ethnicity not listed here

What is your current field of study?

- BSc: Computer Science (AI, CS, Computational, Security)

- BSc: Social Science (Communication Science, Psychology)
- MSc: Computer Science (AI, CS, Computational, Security)
- MSc: Social Science (Communication Science, Psychology)
- Other:

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
When you have a problem to solve, one of the first things you do is get as many facts about the problem as possible.	<input type="radio"/>				
When you are attempting to find a solution to the problem, you usually try to think of as many different approaches to the problem as possible.	<input type="radio"/>				
When making decisions, you generally use a systematic method for judging and comparing alternatives.	<input type="radio"/>				
After carrying out a solution to the problem, you usually try to analyze what went right and what went wrong.	<input type="radio"/>				

Raffle

Under all participants we are giving away 5 x 10€, 5 x 20€, 1 x 50€ and 1 x 100€ gift card (VVV Cadeau) that you can spend on your favorite webshops! **DISCLAIMER:** Only fully completed submissions (“Your response has been recorded”) will be considered for the prize.

If you want to participate in the raffle please provide your STUDENT email. Your responses will not be linked to your email (we only use it to determine the winner). Private emails will not be accepted to participate in the raffle.

STUDENT Email Address:

Debriefing?

Debriefing

You have successfully completed the survey. Thank you very much for being part of this study!

The aim of this study is twofold:

- Phishing susceptibility and risk perception.
- Identifying to what extent a human factors (i.e. gender) effect learning about cybersecurity.

As participants you have been assigned to one of two conditions: a male instructor, or a female instructor teaching about phishing mails. This study will compare the differences and similarities in outcomes of these two

conditions.

We would kindly ask you to not share the design of this study with potential fellow participants.

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